

Efficient Cross-Architecture Binary Function Embeddings through Knowledge Distillation

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ABSTRACT

Deep learning has recently been shown to be effective in various tasks related to static binary analysis. One important analysis task is the binary function similarity problem: Given the binary code of two functions compiled with different compilers, different settings, and different processor architectures, the goal is to decide whether the functions are semantically equivalent (i.e. "similar") or not. This problem has numerous applications for embedded systems, for example plagiarism detection, validation of compliance restrictions with usable software licenses, more efficient reverse engineering of existing binary codebases, or vulnerability scanning by detecting known vulnerable functions. In this paper, we propose a novel training scheme for the popular transformer neural network architecture to learn function embeddings directly from instruction listings. Unlike existing approaches, our solution explicitly considers the cross-architecture scenario: we propose a training method to adapt the model to different instruction set architectures (ISA) without having to train a new model from scratch, which allows the model to also be used efficiently for embedded systems, where there are a variety of different processor architectures. We show that our solution achieves a similarity classification accuracy of **89.6%** on a dataset consisting of several real-world open source software projects. Finally, we conduct extensive experiments to demonstrate the effectiveness of knowledge distillation in increasing the computational efficiency of the embedding model. We demonstrate a reduction in the number of parameters from **87M** to **23M**, while still maintaining a classification accuracy of **87.8%**. Our code and artifacts are available as open source¹.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Security and privacy** → **Software reverse engineering**; • **Software and its engineering** → *Automated static analysis*.

¹<https://github.com/securityinmobility/autobert-binary-embedding>

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KEYWORDS

Deep Learning, Static Analysis, Function Recognition, Binary Function Similarity Detection

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1 INTRODUCTION

Evaluating software security is a fundamentally important task during the development and operation of computer systems. A commonly used method to assess the security of software is the process of vulnerability scanning, i.e. searching for known vulnerabilities in different forms: if available, source code can be used to detect security weaknesses with methods such as manual reviews or tool-assisted static and dynamic analysis. However, source code is not always available for inspection for many different reasons: Malware authors want to provide as little information as possible that could be used during the analysis. Commercial software aims to protect intellectual property by making the software available exclusively as binary files. This means that functions cannot be easily integrated into the competitor's software. For embedded devices, the firmware is usually not provided to the end user. Binaries in these categories are regularly distributed as stripped binaries, possibly statically linked (i.e. without any useful symbols).

During vulnerability scanning, one fundamental challenge is to decide whether a given vulnerable program code is included in the application. A building block of this task is the binary function similarity problem: Taking as input the binary representation of a pair of functions, the objective is to produce a numeric value as output that captures the "similarity" between them. Reverse engineers use code similarity metrics to match an unknown function to (labeled) functions in previously generated databases to save time during the analysis. Ideally, a function should only be analyzed and labeled once. In general, the binary similarity problem is challenging to solve: source code compiled with different compilers and different settings such as optimization level or flags that affect code generation produces varying binary code. This is especially

true for code that is compiled for different instruction-set architectures. Traditional approaches, such as pattern matching on bytes, are thus ineffective.

Recently, there have been many advances in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) using different types of machine learning models for various tasks. One class of models that has shown promising results for sequence-to-sequence modeling tasks (such as text-language translation) are the so-called Transformer models. Since binary code is essentially the machine language of a given CPU, it is a natural idea to utilize neural machine translation (NMT) to automatically learn a translation from binary code to a different representation, while conserving semantic information that can be used to evaluate the similarity of two given binary functions. NMT models typically consist of an encoder-decoder scheme, where the encoder takes the (preprocessed) input of the model in the source domain and translates it into an intermediate representation that contains rich semantic information in the form of a context vector or matrix. The decoder then takes the intermediate representation and tries to reconstruct the information contained in the target domain. For NMT tasks, this architecture is commonly known as a sequence-to-sequence model. It is obvious that all the information for the decoder is contained in the context matrix of the model. It therefore seems logical that the context matrix can be used to derive semantic information that is also valuable for the binary function similarity task.

To the best of our knowledge, there exists no published solution that addresses all the preceding requirements. To this end, we present AutoBERT, a pretrained assembly language model for function embedding, which is based on the BERT NLP model [5]. We focus on the binary function similarity problem and specifically aim to support the efficient inclusion of additional instruction set architectures after initial training. Our AutoBERT model is motivated by an application for vulnerability scanning in the automotive domain (thus the name) where firmware comes in a large number of different binary formats and instruction set architectures. Because code reuse is common in the automotive industry [19], being able to detect known vulnerable code included in the firmware of different electronic control units (with different microcontrollers and instruction set architectures) is especially useful for this context.

The contributions of this paper are the following:

- We propose the application and a training method for the established BERT model to efficiently solve the cross architecture binary function identification task.
- **We propose a new training scheme to allow the efficient extension of the model for additional instruction-set architectures.**
- We train the model and quantitatively evaluate it on two datasets that have previously been published and used in a similar setting. We believe that this allows for the comparison of our model with existing solutions to some extent.
- We conducted several experiments in knowledge distillation to reduce the computational effort of the model, which makes our solution feasible to be used in real-world applications.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: we present related work in Section 2, explain the methodology and the training process in section 3, and evaluate the trained models by an

intrinsic and extrinsic measurement in section 4. We discuss limitations of our work in Section 5 and conclude in Section 6.

2 RELATED WORK

In this section we introduce some basic background on function embedding and discuss related works on the application of machine learning models as an approach. Based on the discussions, we summarize some pitfalls and open challenges in this field.

The embedding generation process generally consists of the following three steps:

- (1) Pre-processing and feature extraction
- (2) Instruction / Basic Block Encoding
- (3) Function Embedding from Instruction Features

For each of the steps, there exist different approaches. We broadly divide the identified works in the literature into those that propose embedding-based solutions and those that do not.

Classical Approaches. that do not utilize machine learning often require hand-crafted features that are selected by domain experts. For example, BinDiff [7, 8] uses 13 different functions level features with varying weights to match functions, including a hash matching of the original raw function bytes, the number of basic blocks, the number of edges between those blocks and the number of calls to sub-functions. The features are then used to perform a sub-graph matching to recall the correct function. Although this method generally proves effective with functions built by the same compiler for identical platforms, they hardly generalize across different architectures or compilers (see [3]) and solving the graph isomorphism problem for each pair of functions is prohibitively computationally expensive. Pewny et al. propose a method called Tree Edit Distance Based Equational Matching (TEDEM) [21], where each vertex of a control flow graph (CFG) is represented with an expression tree; they then use the tree edit distances as a metric for code similarity. This approach requires a preprocessing phase, where the code of the basic blocks is reduced by symbolic simplification. This step has to be implemented accordingly for each supported architecture and requires manual work. David et al. [3] instead propose to use dynamic behavior of the function, by collecting several indicators from running several independent execution traces (tracelets). The functions are then ranked by comparing the edit distance between tracelets. Intuitively, this method should be able to identify functions that have a similar behavior during runtime. However, it requires the ability to at least emulate the code, which might be difficult for uncommon architectures. A similar method was proposed by Egele et al. [9], where each function is executed multiple times with random arguments. It is unclear whether identified features can be used effectively in a cross-architecture scenario [17]. David et al. later modified their approach to work on an architecture-independent intermediate representation [4]. A function is sampled into slices of independent code runs, called *strands*. By minimizing common strands across the dataset, a function is identified by the remaining unique strands. This approach is limited in that a function signature might not be constant in size but could consist of multiple unique strands,

which could impact matching robustness, especially in optimization scenarios where code is eliminated (most importantly inlining). Furthermore, the strand semantics are only useful in this specific task setting.

Machine Learning approaches. Lately, there have been numerous research efforts that have successfully applied machine learning to various binary analysis tasks [2, 12, 22, 24]. The importance of the binary similarity problem is reflected by the quantity of available literature. An overview of the different machine learning approaches for instruction embedding is given in Table 1. Feng et al. first proposed Genius [11] in 2016. They use several basic-block level features (such as the number of string and numeric constants), as well as structural features of the control flow graph like the number of offsprings for each basic block to compute high-level features for each function. The feature vectors of the basic blocks for a function are then “collapsed” by calculating a centroid of the vectors. Xu et al. propose Gemini [30], which uses the same features as Genius [11]. Instead of simply averaging the vectors, they instead use a Graph Neural Network called Structure2Vec [25] that combines the basic block feature vectors into a single function embedding. Ding et al. present ASM2VEC [6]. They used the PVD-DM model [13] to generate instruction embeddings and an embedding for the function containing these instructions simultaneously. Asm2Vec shows promising results but is limited to an instruction representation that consists of one opcode and up to two operands, which does not hold true on all platforms, e.g. ARM or MIPS which have a 3-operand design. Representation Learning of Instructions has recently received increased attention. Lee et al. use a method called Instruction2vec [14], that adopts a popular concept from NLP, called word2vec [18]. Each instruction is encoded as a vector with nine dimensions, by first splitting the instruction into the opcode and operands, respectively, which are represented by a unique index number. Using the continuous bag-of-words (CBOW) model, the encoding learns to embed context information for each instruction. This approach is also used by Massarelli et al. in SAFE [17] and Zuo et al. in NMT4BINARIES [31].

Generally speaking, the existing approaches can be distinguished along a number of choices:

- **The underlying algorithm:** BinDiff [8], a well-known commercial tool for binary code comparison, uses a graph-theoretical approach (fuzzy subgraph matching) to compare the attributed control flow graphs of the binaries. Disassembler/Decompiler tools, such as IDA Pro’s F.L.I.R.T.² or Ghidra³ Function ID, use pattern matching by calculating a fuzzy hash over the function prologue bytes. Recent approaches use deep learning with different neural networks to express the binary similarity problem as a machine learning problem. In the remainder of this work, we focus on this solution as they have been reported to achieve promising results. We identify two important requirements for such a solution to be useful in the context of embedded software:
- **Input format of the binaries:** ranges from mostly raw bytes [22] to extensive pre-processing, e.g. by reconstructing the CFG of the binary and manually extracting different features of the contained basic blocks. Intuitively, a solution that automatically

learns to extract relevant features is more attractive for two reasons: (1) it reduces the necessity for manual feature engineering, which requires expert knowledge and significant effort; and (2) it improves the portability of the solution: instead of manually adopting to additional compilers or instruction set architectures, a machine learning approach can simply be re-trained or fine-tuned, thus increasing the efficiency of the approach.

- **Matching across different instruction set architectures:** whether the proposed solution works on a single processor architecture, or can be used to recognize semantically similar functions across different CPU architectures.

Finally, Li et al. proposed PALMTREE [16]. They use a BERT model with three distinct pretraining tasks to learn an instruction embedding model that efficiently captures semantic information about the instructions. Their solution is similar to the one we chose for AutoBERT, with three important differences:

- (1) During training, they limit themselves to instruction pairs which they sample using a $N = 2$ sliding window approach over the instructions in a basic block. The instruction pairs within such a context window are selected in different ways (such as a Def-Use relationship). However, in our opinion, adding more context to the instructions can help the model to better learn important semantic relationships between instructions that cannot be expressed by only two instructions. An example of this is shown in the Listing 1. In this function stack frame prologue the push instructions are related to the `sub rsp, 32` instruction, since together they form the `x86_64` function prologue. If the training data only samples instruction pairs, the model cannot learn the relation of the operands (32) and the number of preceding instructions (4).
- (2) Secondly, their solution learns embeddings solely on an instruction level, i.e. identical instructions map to an identical vector regardless of their position or context within a function. The authors address this by combining PalmTree with additional models for an application in downstream tasks (such as the Binary Similarity Problem). Since AutoBERT focuses on function recognition, we calculate the embedding vector from the complete set of instructions of a given function.
- (3) Lastly, PalmTree only supports the x86-architecture. AutoBERT extends upon this by providing a training method that allows the inclusion of additional architectures.

Note that PalmTree and AutoBERT are not necessarily competing solutions; in fact, the training tasks proposed by Li et al. can be used equally to train the instruction encoding for AutoBERT.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overview

In the following section, we elaborate on our design considerations.

To address the challenges summarized in Section 1, we developed AutoBERT, a deep neural network based on the BERT [5] model, that learns semantically rich function embeddings directly from instruction listings with minimal preprocessing. This decision

²<https://hex-rays.com/ida-pro/>

³<https://ghidra-sre.org/>

Table 1: Summary of Approaches (based on [16]).

Name	Encoding	Structure	Context	Disassembly required
Instruction2Vec [14]	manual	yes	no	yes
SAFE [17]	word2vec	no	control flow	yes
Asm2Vec [6]	PV-DM	partial	control flow	yes
PalmTree [16]	BERT	yes	control flow & data flow	yes
AutoBERT (this work)	BERT, MiniLMv2	yes	control flow	yes

is due to our use case: for uncommon processor architectures, there is often only basic support available in reverse engineering / static analysis tools. This makes it difficult to use more high-level features, such as control flow graphs or data dependency graphs [16], as well as any dynamic features, such as execution traces [20]. Assembly language, however, is basically a 1:1 mapping from the binary representations of the machine code. Given a documentation of the supported instructions for a CPU and their respective binary encoding, building a disassembler is possible with reasonable effort. Additionally, free and commercially available reverse engineering tools such as Ghidra, IDA Pro or objdump already support disassembling for a large number of processors.

Inspired by the large success recently shown by Large Language Models (LLMs) in various tasks, we aligned AutoBERT with concepts that are well established in the field of NLP. During the design, we use the following correspondence: A function is considered as a *document*, that consists of multiple *sentences* (instructions), that are formed from *words* (operations and operands). Each *word* is formed by one or multiple tokens.

The objective for our network is to generate meaningful function embeddings that are invariant to changes such as the usage of different compilers, optimization and other code generation settings and can be compared across different instruction-set architectures. In order for our deep neural network to understand the internal structure and semantics of instructions, the model must be able to capture all relevant information contained within an instruction statement and its context.

Listing 1: Token masking in a typical x86_64 function prologue (Intel syntax)

```

mov    [rsp + 8], rcx
push   r15
push   r14
push   r13
sub    <MASK>, 32
lea   r13, 128[rsp]

```

For large language models, the method of pretraining has been shown to be effective in learning a language representation that can be used in downstream tasks. For this, the training task for a language model is typically split into two phases:

(1) the pretraining phase, where the model is training in a weakly supervised fashion on a large amount of data on different tasks that are unrelated to the model’s final task. For our solution, we make use of a recently proposed training task in NLP, which is also used in the original BERT paper [5]: Masked Language Modeling. This task trains a language model to predict the masked (missing) tokens within a list of instructions. Intuitively speaking, this task

motivates the model to capture context information for a given token. Listing 1 demonstrates the idea behind this pretraining task. Given the disassembly listing of some binary code, we randomly mask a token from the input to the model (*rsp*, in red). We train the model to predict the missing token, which forces the model to consider the context of the function. In this example, our model learns that the sub-instruction can take registers (*rsp*) as an operand and is used in the context of a function prologue to reserve stack space for local variables.

(2) After pretraining, the model is fine-tuned for a specific, so-called downstream, task. In the case of AutoBERT this task is motivated by the binary similarity problem: we want the model to output an embedding vector that maps semantically identical (or “similar”) functions to vectors that are spatially close to each other. We consider two functions similar if they are compiled from identical source code, regardless of processor architecture, compiler, or optimization flags. We acknowledge that this simplification might not hold for every sample in our dataset, for example with common functions contained in two different libraries which are semantically equivalent.

This approach allows a new architecture to be added by training an additional model on a dataset, which contains aligned samples of the anchor architecture and the new target architecture. This dataset can be collected more easily by compiling an existing corpus of source code with different compilers for the target architecture. With this approach, any already existing models do not need to be re-trained when adding another ISA, as they share a common anchor model that is used as the reference for the embeddings. During our research, we encountered code for at least 6 different microcontroller architectures in a dataset⁴ consisting of firmware files for a modern car.

- x86-64 (Infotainment)
- ARM (Infotainment, ADAS, HMI)
- Tricore (Engine, ADAS)
- PowerPC (Body)
- V850 / RH850 (Body)
- FR81S (HMI)

We address this specific challenge in Step 2 of our training process (see Figure 2): While the anchor model for the binary code similarity decision problem can be trained for a more common processor architecture (such as x86 in our case), the student model only learns to align the generated function embeddings with the output of the anchor model. The aligned dataset (Dataset Architecture #2 in Figure 2) can be created by simply using different compilers targeting the anchor and student CPU architectures. Since our model

⁴ODX Flash containers without symbols

directly learns from instructions listings, no additional tool support is required for the student architecture.

Figure 1 gives an overview of the design of AutoBERT. There are four main components: The input preparation, tokenization and normalization of the input, the language model and the training process. In the following sections, we will present details for each of the components.

3.2 Input Processing

To use our network on the code from binary files, we first disassemble them. In this step, the flat binary file is split into code and data sections, and boundaries of the individual functions are identified. Note that this is not necessarily a trivial task when working with binary formats that do not contain segment information, such as embedded firmware images. This is a field of active research and there are approaches that also employ machine learning for this task [28]. For this paper, we used existing datasets (see Table 2) to ensure comparability of our approach with existing publications. These datasets contain ELF-files with symbols, providing ground truth about the contained functions and their offset addresses. The ground truth is only used during the sampling process for the dataset splits and not during the actual network training. For each function, we do a linear disassembly sweep to extract the instructions in text form. Since there is no standardized representation for assembly instructions, there are slight variations in the assembly code that is generated by different disassemblers. We address this issue in the normalization step.

3.3 Tokenization and Normalization

Existing works use different strategies when tokenizing individual instructions (see Table 1). We follow an approach that is similar to the one proposed in PalmTree [16] and is applicable to most assembly syntaxes: each individual instruction is divided into an opcode and a number of operands. Complex operands that contain additional modifiers, such as a displacement offset, are further divided. For instance, the instruction `"lea r13, , 1, 2, 8, [, rsp]"` is split into the tokens `lea, r13, ,, 1, 2, 8, [, rsp` and `]`. Hence, each supported opcode of the ISA is represented as an individual token. To address the Out-of-Vocabulary (OOV) problem that can occur when an operand can not be represented by the tokens in the vocabulary learned during training, we use a normalization strategy that is also found in existing works [14, 17]: we replace references to string and data constants with a special token `"<addr>"`, and `call/jump` targets are replaced with `"<func>"` to prevent accidental label leaks in the training datasets. In addition, we normalize the numbers that are represented in hex or octal format and split them into individual digits. The motivation for this is the self-attention mechanism of our model: it should be able to learn to reduce attention for digit combinations that do not carry significant useful information. We acknowledge that this is a deviation from the pre-processing pipelines in previous works [16, 17].

3.4 Model

The proposed solution is not limited to a specific model architecture. The main model we use in our experiments is based on the BERT model [5], a well established transformer language model.

This choice is motivated by the success and versatility the model has shown in various applications and the size of the model so that it can still be trained on a moderately powerful machine in a reasonable amount of time. Transformer models, first proposed by Vaswani et al. [26], heavily use the multi-head self-attention mechanism: each head processes an identical input tensor consisting of the input tokens and a positional encoding of each token. The different heads capture different aspects of the input sequence, by assigning attention values in a way that makes their output useful for a decoder. Additionally to the position information, which just contains information about the position of the current token in the sequence, we pass information about instruction boundaries by introducing special tokens as delimiters: the `"<cls>"` token is used to signal the start of a sequence, and the `"<sep>"` token separates the individual instructions.

To support the masked-language-modeling task, we add a softmax classification layer on top of the encoder output during pre-training. This layer predicts the normalized probabilities for each token in the vocabulary at the masked token position. We use cross-entropy loss during the training for this task, i.e. the training objective is to minimize the difference between the predicted and target tokens.

For the downstream task (Binary Function Identification), this final layer is removed. At this point, the model's encoder produces a sequence of hidden state outputs, depending on the amount of supplied tokens and the number of attention heads. There are several methods to retrieve a fixed-size representation from this: a commonly used solution is to use the embedding of the last `"<sep>"` token as the output, since this token accumulates the information of all the previous tokens. However, we decided to use a mean-pooling layer, that simply averages the embeddings of all the tokens, and an additional dense linear layer to reduce the dimension of the output layer. This allows our model to generate more compact function embedding vectors and decouples our solution from internal implementation details of the underlying model. Previous work [16] suggests that reducing the output dimension does not noticeably decrease the model performance in this setting.

3.5 Training

The actual training for the binary similarity detection task is also done in a two step process (shown in 2:

(1) first we train an anchor model for a single instruction-set architecture, that sets the baseline for the embedding process. To convert the training process to a self-supervised one, we use a Triplet-Loss training objective similar to previous works [17]. That is: for each function in our dataset (**anchor function** a), we randomly select one **positive sample** p that we consider similar (i.e. the function was compiled from the same source code, but with a different compiler or options) and another **negative sample** n that stems from a different function. The objective of the loss function (shown in Equation 1) is to ensure that the distance d between the anchor vector \vec{a} and the negative sample \vec{n} is greater than the distance between the anchor and the positive sample \vec{p} by a margin ϵ . The margin is a hyperparameter that should be tuned in different training runs. For our experiments, we used the Euclidean distance as the distance metric d and $\epsilon = 5.0$ as a baseline threshold [23].

Figure 1: AutoBERT solution overview

Figure 2: Overview of the training process showing the first step for training the x86 anchor model and the second step using knowledge distillation to train a student model with support for additional instruction set architectures.

$$L_{triplet} = \max(d(\vec{a}, \vec{p}) - d(\vec{a}, \vec{n}) + \epsilon, 0) \quad (1)$$

In summary, this loss function causes similar functions to be mapped together, whereas the distance to dissimilar functions is maximized.

(2) after training and evaluating the anchor model M , another model \hat{M} (student model) is trained that adds support for the second target architecture. We use the knowledge distillation approach proposed by Reimers and Gurevych in the SENTENCE-TRANSFORMERS framework [23]. We sample our dataset again in the following way: For each function a , we randomly select another function t that we consider similar (again, compiled from the same source code), but this time for a different processor architecture. We feed both samples (anchor a and target t) into the \hat{M} network, and minimize the mean-squared error between the resulting embedding vectors for both a and t within a batch B , as shown in equation 2.

$$L_{MSE} = \frac{1}{|B|} \sum [(M(a) - \hat{M}(a))^2 + (M(a) - \hat{M}(t))^2] \quad (2)$$

The mean-squared error is chosen as the loss function to minimize the deviation between the anchor and target vector embeddings. With this objective, the student model learns to approximate the output of the anchor model for the original architecture, while simultaneously adding support for a different processor architecture. As a positive side effect, the student model does not require a full pretraining run, thus reducing the computational effort. The resulting model (denoted as "AutoBERT Model (multi)" in Figure 1) is hence able to return embeddings for both the anchor architecture and the target architecture.

4 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In this section, we experimentally evaluate the effectiveness of our approach. We try to avoid the usual pitfalls when working with machine learning for cybersecurity [1] as much as possible. To this end, we observe the following principles:

- We use different datasets for pretraining and the downstream task. Each dataset is split into a training and testing dataset (80% training, 20% testing), while ensuring that the functions in the training- and testing dataset are disjunct (P3)
- We benchmark our model against existing solutions by approximating their experimental setup, i.e. by using the identical datasets and metrics (P6)
- We evaluate our model on a real world application, the binary function similarity task (P9)

Our evaluations can be classified into two categories:

(1) intrinsic evaluations that use synthetic metrics as an indicator. We use the loss functions from Section 3 on our testing datasets and additionally report the perplexity (see equation 3) of our pre-trained model which acts as an indicator of how well the pretraining task captures the semantic of the underlying assembly language.

(2) we perform an extrinsic evaluation on the binary similarity task. That is, given the embedding vectors of two functions f_1 and

Table 2: Overview of the used datasets.

Dataset	# of binary samples	Projects	Architectures	Compilers
EKLAVYA [2]	55118	binutils coreutils findutils	x86 x64	gcc clang
MISA [29]	317569	binutils 2.30 coreutils 8.29 ffmpeg n3.2.13 OpenSSL 1.1.1b Redis 5.0.5	x86 x64 ARM	gcc

f_2 , we calculate the euclidean distance between the vectors and use a threshold to perform a binary-label classification. This procedure reflects the evaluations of the related works [15–17, 30]. We report our performance numbers by presenting the ROC curves (receiver operating characteristic) and Area under Curve (AUC) metric of the models in different configurations, i.e. the classifier is evaluated at different similarity thresholds.

All experiments were performed on a machine with an AMD EPYC CPU, 128 GB RAM and a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU. We used Ghidra to disassemble the binaries in our datasets. For training, we use the AdamW-optimizer, a learning rate of 2.0×10^{-4} with a cosine learning rate decay. The warmup period is chosen to be 10% of the epoch length. In addition, a weight decay of 0.1 is applied. We train each of the models for 10 epochs, after which the loss function of the network converges. The training for all models took roughly 24 hours.

$$PPL(X) = \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{t} \sum_i^t \log p_0(x_i | x_{<i})\right\} \quad (3)$$

4.1 Dataset

To ensure the comparability of our approach, we use the EKLAVYA and MISA datasets previously presented [2, 29]. Note that the EKLAVYA dataset only contains x86_64 binaries, whereas MISA has samples for x86_64 and arm. Thus, we used the EKLAVYA dataset for pre-training the x86 anchor model, the MISA dataset for training the multi-architecture model. Table 2 gives a basic overview of the datasets used.

For the binary function identification task, we remove samples that contain less than **13** instructions (the lower decile D_1), as shown in figure 3, since they do not contain enough information that a machine learning model could use to sensibly distinguish these functions. Upon manual inspection, this removes a lot of getter/setter or stub functions from the dataset. We argue that removing those functions is acceptable, since they are usually not interesting when reverse engineering unknown binary code, as they can be easily distinguished by a human reverse engineer. This procedure is in alignment with existing works [10, 16, 17] that we use as a benchmark for our method.

Furthermore, we truncate functions to a maximum of $N = 1024$ tokens, as this is the maximum input size supported by our model. We argue that this still offers enough context for the model to generate useful embedding vectors for the function.

Figure 3: Cumulative Distribution Plot over the number of instructions per function after disassembly. Small functions are removed during preprocessing.

4.2 Evaluation

After pretraining, we calculate the perplexity of the BERT model as the exponentiated average negative log-likelihood of the sequences in our testing datasets (Equation 3). The perplexity generally gives an indication, if the model can accurately predict the next token given all previous tokens as context. We note that the perplexity metric has limited value when dealing with a Fixed-Length model, such as the BERT model, if the observed sequence is longer than the maximum number of tokens supported by the model (context window, $N = 1024$ for our experiments). In our case, this limitation is not applicable because of the truncation during the dataset pre-processing. During our experiments, we observed a perplexity value of $PPL = 1.54$ for the x86 anchor model, confirming a generally promising token prediction performance and encouraging our hypothesis that an LLM can successfully be applied to capture the semantics of an assembly language.

We report the resulting ROC curves for the binary similarity classification problem in Figure 4, using the test datasets presented in Sect. 4.1 in the following way: For each function triplet (anchor, positive, negative), we assign the labels 1 or 0 respectively. We use the euclidean distance between the embedding vectors as the

Figure 4: ROC curves of AutoBERT

classification result and calculate the True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR) at different thresholds.

We observe that AutoBERT achieves good performance on both datasets (Table 3). Interestingly, the classification performance slightly drops on the MISA dataset. We believe that this could be due to the anchor model being solely trained on the EKLAVYA dataset. PalmTree [16] was only evaluated in the x86 setting, since training the model for a different architecture requires tool support for the Def-Use relationship prediction, which Ghidra does not provide.

Furthermore, we report the performance numbers of a MiniLM-L6-v2 model [27] that we trained as a student model using the same knowledge distillation approach (Section 3.5) from the full-size BERT anchor model. This model has significantly fewer layers and parameters, which improves the runtime performance of our solution and proves the effectiveness and generalizability of the proposed training process. For more details, see Section 5.

Table 3: AUC classification performance of the models compared to the baseline.

Model	EKLAVYA	MISA	-x86	-arm
PalmTree	0.946 ⁵	-(not applicable)	0.783	-
AutoBERT	0.957	0.864	0.867	0.852
MiniLM-L6-v2	0.945	0.891	0.883	0.877

5 LIMITATIONS

In this paper, we focus on the cross-architecture binary function similarity task using a large language model. We show that knowledge distillation can be a promising approach to extend existing neural network solutions to additional processor architectures, without having to retrain a new model from scratch. This reduces the

⁵as reported [16]

computational effort and makes this approach feasible for application in special domains, such as reverse engineering firmware for embedded systems in the automotive domain.

However, in this paper, we could only perform a meaningful evaluation of the X86 and ARM architecture. The reason is to ensure comparability of our approach with existing solutions, and the large effort necessary to collect a useful dataset containing samples for additional architectures. To fully evaluate to effectiveness of our approach, more detailed evaluations are necessary, e.g., by adding PowerPC or the TriCore architecture. We plan to create and release a dataset for more uncommon instruction-set architectures in the future.

We believe that our models perform adequately giving the simplicity of the design without any requirements for expert knowledge tuning. The resulting accuracy values (**0.957**) are comparable with the results reported [16] for the x86 architecture (**0.946**), but our approach does not require the addition of new pretraining tasks. We believe that our model profits from the larger context window to learn a useful instruction embedding scheme. Interestingly, the MiniLM-L6-v2 student model performed slightly better on the MISA dataset, despite being distilled from the larger AutoBERT model and having far fewer parameters (**87M** vs **23M**). In our opinion, this could hint towards a slight overfitting of the anchor model on the (smaller) EKLAVYA dataset and suggest this could be alleviated by using a larger and more diverse dataset during pretraining. We leave this also for future work.

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper we have summarized our approach to extend the usage of a large language model for a special use case, namely solving the cross-architecture binary function similarity problem for function identification. To this end, we proposed the AutoBERT model and a novel method to pretrain and fine-tune a transformer model for different instruction set architectures. Our method makes heavy

use of knowledge distillation to increase the computational efficiency. We systematically evaluate AutoBERT on existing datasets and compare our results with existing works. We conclude that AutoBERT can be used as promising technical basis for a tool that increases the efficiency during reverse engineering, by automatically labeling previously seen functions and as a tool for vulnerability scanning by re-identifying known vulnerable functions across different instruction-set architectures.

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